

Minimum Perfect Square Sum Bordered and Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares: Orders 32 to 47

Inder J. Taneja¹

Abstract

*There are many ways of writing magic or **bordered** magic squares, where the sum of entries is always a **perfect square**. In one of the possibility, the magic sums are such that they satisfy **uniformity property**. Another way is to write magic squares generated by **Pythagorean triples**. Based on these idea, we can always write magic squares or **bordered** magic squares where the sum of entries is always a **perfect square**. Still, these sums are not minimum. There is a third way to write magic squares or **bordered** squares such that we get **minimum perfect square sum** of entries. This what we have done in this work with **bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares. In case of even order magic squares, we can always write **block-wise bordered** magic squares with equal sum sub-blocks [25]. In case of odd order magic squares, we can write them as **block-wise bordered** magic squares, but with different sub-blocks sums [?]. This work is for the magic squares of orders 32 to 47. The work on magic squares of orders 3 to 31 is given in another works [?]. Recently, author [29] applied this idea of **perfect square sum** of entries to write area representations of magic squares.*

¹Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012). Also worked at Delhi University, India (1976-1978).

E-mail: ijtaneja@gmail.com;

Web-sites: <http://inderjtaneja.com>;

Twitter: @IJTANEJA;

Instagram: @crazynumbers.

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1 Perfect Square Sum of Entries

In this section, we shall write different ways to obtain magic squares in such a way that sums of entries turns to be a **perfect square**. This process is given in following three subsection in different way.

1.1 Uniformity Property

In [27], the author showed that magic square with entries sum a **perfect square** can be constructed in different ways. These are summarized in following results.

Result 1. A magic square with **perfect square sum** of entries given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Magic Square Order:} & \quad k; \\
 \text{Odd numbers entries:} & \quad M := \{1, 3, 5, \dots, 2k^2 - 3, 2k^2 - 1\}; \\
 \text{Natural numbers entries:} & \quad K := \left\{ \frac{k^2 + 1}{2}, \frac{k^2 + 3}{2}, \dots, \frac{3(k^2 - 1)}{2} - 1, \frac{3k^2 - 1}{2} \right\}; \\
 \text{Magic Square Sum:} & \quad \mathbf{S}_{k \times k} := k^3; \\
 \text{Total Entries Sum:} & \quad \mathbf{T}_{k^2} := k^4.
 \end{aligned}$$

For simplicity, let's represent the **uniformity** as,

$$\langle k, k^2, k^3, k^4 \rangle \tag{1}$$

where

- $k \rightarrow$ **order of a magic square;**
- $k^2 \rightarrow$ **total number of entries;**
- $k^3 \rightarrow$ **magic square sum;**
- $k^4 \rightarrow$ **sum of all the entries of a magic square.**

It happens with following situations:

- (i) magic squares with **consecutive odd numbers** entries starting from 1.
- (ii) magic squares with **consecutive natural numbers** obtained based on odd numbers entries having the same magic sum.

1.2 Pythagorean Triples

The Result 1 is known as magic square with **uniformity property**. There may be many **Pythagorean triples** satisfying sum of magic squares. But not necessarily, these **Pythagorean triples** generates magic squares of same order. Recently, author studied a result where **Pythagorean triples** generating magic squares and the sum of entries are **perfect squares**. This result is given below.

Result 2. A general formula relating **Pythagorean triples** and magic squares given by

$$F(n, k) := (n(2k + n), 2k(k + n), 2k(k + n) + n^2), k \in \mathbf{N}_+, \tag{2}$$

where n is the order of a magic square and k is the gap between two consecutive term of two consecutive **Pythagorean triples** representing same order magic squares. The right side of the function $F(n, k)$ is written in terms of a **Pythagorean triple**, i.e., (a, b, c) .

The entries of magic squares are given by

$$E_1(n, k) := \{4k(k+n) + 1, 4k(k+n) + 3, \dots, 4k(k+n) + 2n^2 - 3, 4k(k+n) + 2n^2 - 1\};$$

$$E_2(n, k) := \left\{4k(k+n) + \frac{n^2 + 1}{2}, 4k(k+n) + \frac{n^2 + 3}{2}, \dots, 4k(k+n) + \frac{3(n^2 - 1)}{2}, 4k(k+n) + \frac{3n^2 - 1}{2}\right\}.$$

The entries $E_1(n, k)$ are for all order magic squares resulting in **consecutive odd numbers**. The entries $E_2(n, k)$ are only for **odd order magic squares** resulting in **consecutive natural numbers**. In this case, the sum of entries is the same in both the situations. In this case, we don't have **uniformity property** given in (??). For $k = 1$, the **generated** magic squares are with **minimum perfect square sum** of entries satisfying **Pythagorean triples** property. For details refer [26, 27].

The **minimum value** of sums entries is a **perfect square** in relation to **Pythagorean triples** property, but it may be bigger than the one obtained by applying Result 1. There is another way where we can get **perfect square sum** of entries of a magic square not necessarily satisfying **uniformity property** or **Pythagorean triples** property. This process is given below.

1.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let us consider

$$\begin{aligned} G(n, k) &= T(n) - T(n - k) \\ &= (n - k + 1) + (n - k + 3) + \dots + n \\ &= k \left(n - \frac{k - 1}{2} \right), \quad n \geq k, \\ &= \frac{k}{2} (2n - k + 1), \quad n \geq k \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where

$$T_n := 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots + n = \frac{n(n + 1)}{2}, \quad n \geq 1 \tag{4}$$

The expression (4) is well known sum of the series of positive natural numbers. It is sometimes known as **Pascal's triangle** property.

Result 3. Let's consider,

$$L(n, k) := \left(\sqrt{k}, n - k + 1, n, \frac{G(n, k)^2}{\sqrt{k}}, G(n, k)^2, \sqrt{G(n, k)} \right), \quad (5)$$

where $n = m^2 + \frac{p^2-1}{2}$, $k = p^2$ and p is the order of a magic square. The first positive values obtained by considering m , $m \in \mathbf{N}_+$ in expression (5) lead us to a magic square with **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

For simplicity, let's write $L(a, b, c, d, e, f)$, for the representations given in expression (5), where

$$\begin{aligned} a &\rightarrow \text{Order of magic square;} & a &= \sqrt{k}; \\ b &\rightarrow \text{First member of a sequence;} & b &= n - k + 1; \\ c &\rightarrow \text{Last member of a sequence;} & c &= n; \\ d &\rightarrow \text{Sum of magic square;} & d &= \frac{G(n, k)^2}{\sqrt{k}}; \\ e &\rightarrow \text{Sum of entries;} & e &= G(n, k)^2; \\ f &\rightarrow \text{Uniformity property, } a = f \text{ or } m = p; \sqrt{k} = \sqrt{G(n, k)}. \end{aligned} \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

1.4 Examples

In Subsections 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3 there are three Results 1, 2 and 3. These results lead us to five different ways of writing magic squares where the sum of entries is always a **perfect square sum**.

Let's consider a **bordered** magic square of orders 8 and 9 with entries, $\{1, 2, \dots, 63\}$ and $\{1, 2, \dots, 80\}$

58	63	3	1	14	52	12	57
55	45	21	48	15	47	19	10
56	42	38	25	28	39	23	9
61	24	31	36	33	30	41	4
11	22	35	32	29	34	43	54
6	16	26	37	40	27	49	59
5	46	44	17	50	18	20	60
8	2	62	64	51	13	53	7

72	2	4	6	7	70	68	66	74
67	58	18	20	21	56	54	60	15
69	55	50	46	31	30	48	27	13
71	57	35	38	43	42	47	25	11
73	59	33	45	41	37	49	23	9
5	19	53	40	39	44	29	63	77
3	17	34	36	51	52	32	65	79
1	22	64	62	61	26	28	24	81
8	80	78	76	75	12	14	16	10

The magic and total entries sums are given by

$$\begin{aligned} S_{8 \times 8} &:= 260; & T_{64} &:= 8 \times 260 = 2080; \\ S_{6 \times 6} &:= 195; & T_{36} &:= 6 \times 195 = 1170; \\ S_{4 \times 4} &:= 130; & T_{16} &:= 4 \times 130 = 520; \\ & & T_4 &:= 130. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} S_{9 \times 9} &:= 369; & T_{81} &:= 9 \times 369 = 3321; \\ S_{7 \times 7} &:= 287; & T_{49} &:= 7 \times 287 = 2009; \\ S_{5 \times 5} &:= 205; & T_{25} &:= 5 \times 205 = 1435; \\ S_{3 \times 3} &:= 123; & T_9 &:= 3 \times 123 = 369; \\ & & T_1 &:= 41. \end{aligned}$$

From above two examples we observe that the sum of all entries in each is not a perfect squares. The following examples lead us to total sum of entries is always a perfect square but in different situations.

(i) Below are **bordered** magic square of orders 8 with entries, $\{1, 3, \dots, 125, 127\}$ and $\{65/2, 67/2, \dots, 189/2, 191/2\}$ satisfying **uniformity property** given in (1)

115	125	5	1	27	103	23	113
109	89	41	95	29	93	37	19
111	83	75	49	55	77	45	17
121	47	61	71	65	59	81	7
21	43	69	63	57	67	85	107
11	31	51	73	79	53	97	117
9	91	87	33	99	35	39	119
15	3	123	127	101	25	105	13

89,5	94,5	34,5	32,5	45,5	83,5	43,5	88,5
86,5	76,5	52,5	79,5	46,5	78,5	50,5	41,5
87,5	73,5	69,5	56,5	59,5	70,5	54,5	40,5
92,5	55,5	62,5	67,5	64,5	61,5	72,5	35,5
42,5	53,5	66,5	63,5	60,5	65,5	74,5	85,5
37,5	47,5	57,5	68,5	71,5	58,5	80,5	90,5
36,5	77,5	75,5	48,5	81,5	49,5	51,5	91,5
39,5	33,5	93,5	95,5	82,5	44,5	84,5	38,5

In both the examples, the magic and total sum entries are the same. See below:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{8 \times 8} &:= 512 = 8^3; & T_{64} &:= 8 \times 512 = 4096 = 64^2 = 8^4; \\ S_{6 \times 6} &:= 384; & T_{36} &:= 6 \times 384 = 2304 = 48^2; \\ S_{4 \times 4} &:= 256; & T_{16} &:= 4 \times 256 = 1024 = 32^2; \\ & & T_4 &:= 256 = 16^2. \end{aligned}$$

Both the examples satisfy the **uniformity property** given in (1), i.e., $\langle 8, 8^2, 8^3, 8^4 \rangle$.

(ii) Below are **bordered** magic square of orders 9 with entries, $\{1, 3, \dots, 159, 161\}$ and $\{41, 42, \dots, 119, 121\}$ satisfying **uniformity property** given in (1)

143	3	7	11	13	139	135	131	147
133	115	35	39	41	111	107	119	29
137	109	99	91	61	59	95	53	25
141	113	69	75	85	83	93	49	21
145	117	65	89	81	73	97	45	17
9	37	105	79	77	87	57	125	153
5	33	67	71	101	103	63	129	157
1	43	127	123	121	51	55	47	161
15	159	155	151	149	23	27	31	19

112	42	44	46	47	110	108	106	114
107	98	58	60	61	96	94	100	55
109	95	90	86	71	70	88	67	53
111	97	75	78	83	82	87	65	51
113	99	73	85	81	77	89	63	49
45	59	93	80	79	84	69	103	117
43	57	74	76	91	92	72	105	119
41	62	104	102	101	66	68	64	121
48	120	118	116	115	52	54	56	50

In both the examples, the magic and total sum of entries are the same. See below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{9 \times 9} &:= 729 = 9^3; & T_{81} &:= 9 \times 729 = 6561 = 81^2 = 9^4; \\
 S_{7 \times 7} &:= 567; & T_{49} &:= 7 \times 567 = 3969 = 63^2; \\
 S_{5 \times 5} &:= 405; & T_{25} &:= 5 \times 405 = 2025 = 45^2; \\
 S_{3 \times 3} &:= 243; & T_9 &:= 3 \times 243 = 729 = 27^2; \\
 & & T_1 &:= 81 = 9^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Both the examples satisfy the **uniformity property** given in (1), i.e., $\langle 9, 9^2, 9^3, 9^4 \rangle$.

(iii) Below are **bordered** magic square of orders 8 with entries, $\{37, 39, \dots, 161, 163\}$ and $\{137/2, 139/2, \dots, 261/2, 263/2\}$ generated by **Pythagorean triple (18, 80, 82)** with least sum of entries:

151	161	41	37	63	139	59	149
145	125	77	131	65	129	73	55
147	119	111	85	91	113	81	53
157	83	97	107	101	95	117	43
57	79	105	99	93	103	121	143
47	67	87	109	115	89	133	153
45	127	123	69	135	71	75	155
51	39	159	163	137	61	141	49

125,5	130,5	70,5	68,5	81,5	119,5	79,5	124,5
122,5	112,5	88,5	115,5	82,5	114,5	86,5	77,5
123,5	109,5	105,5	92,5	95,5	106,5	90,5	76,5
128,5	91,5	98,5	103,5	100,5	97,5	108,5	71,5
78,5	89,5	102,5	99,5	96,5	101,5	110,5	121,5
73,5	83,5	93,5	104,5	107,5	94,5	116,5	126,5
72,5	113,5	111,5	84,5	117,5	85,5	87,5	127,5
75,5	69,5	129,5	131,5	118,5	80,5	120,5	74,5

In both the examples, the magic and total sum entries are the same. See below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= 800; & T_{64} &:= 8 \times 800 = 6400 = 80^2; \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= 600; & T_{36} &:= 6 \times 600 = 3600 = 60^2; \\
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= 400; & T_{16} &:= 4 \times 400 = 1600 = 40^2; \\
 & & T_4 &:= 1600 := 40^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

(iv) Below are **bordered** magic square of orders 9 with entries, $\{41, 43, \dots, 199, 201\}$ and $\{81, 82, \dots, 160, 161\}$ generated by **Pythagorean triple (20, 99, 101)** with least sum of entries:

183	43	47	51	53	179	175	171	187
173	155	75	79	81	151	147	159	69
177	149	139	131	101	99	135	93	65
181	153	109	115	125	123	133	89	61
185	157	105	129	121	113	137	85	57
49	77	145	119	117	127	97	165	193
45	73	107	111	141	143	103	169	197
41	83	167	163	161	91	95	87	201
55	199	195	191	189	63	67	71	59

152	82	84	86	87	150	148	146	154
147	138	98	100	101	136	134	140	95
149	135	130	126	111	110	128	107	93
151	137	115	118	123	122	127	105	91
153	139	113	125	121	117	129	103	89
85	99	133	120	119	124	109	143	157
83	97	114	116	131	132	112	145	159
81	102	144	142	141	106	108	104	161
88	160	158	156	155	92	94	96	90

In both the examples, the magic and total sum of entries are the same. See below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{9 \times 9} &:= 1089 = 9^3; & T_{81} &:= 9 \times 1089 = 9801 = 99^2; \\
 S_{7 \times 7} &:= 847; & T_{49} &:= 7 \times 847 = 5929 = 77^2; \\
 S_{5 \times 5} &:= 605; & T_{25} &:= 5 \times 605 = 3025 = 55^2; \\
 S_{3 \times 3} &:= 363; & T_9 &:= 3 \times 363 = 1089 = 33^2; \\
 & & T_1 &:= 121 = 11^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

(v) Let's consider a **bordered** magic square of orders 8 and 9 with entries, $\{9/2, 11/2, \dots, 133/2, 135/2\}$ and $\{9, 10, \dots, 88, 89\}$ with **minimum perfect square sum** of entries:

61,5	66,5	6,5	4,5	17,5	55,5	15,5	60,5
58,5	48,5	24,5	51,5	18,5	50,5	22,5	13,5
59,5	45,5	41,5	28,5	31,5	42,5	26,5	12,5
64,5	27,5	34,5	39,5	36,5	33,5	44,5	7,5
14,5	25,5	38,5	35,5	32,5	37,5	46,5	57,5
9,5	19,5	29,5	40,5	43,5	30,5	52,5	62,5
8,5	49,5	47,5	20,5	53,5	21,5	23,5	63,5
11,5	5,5	65,5	67,5	54,5	16,5	56,5	10,5

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= 288; & T_{64} &:= 8 \times 288 = 2304 = 48^2; \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= 216; & T_{36} &:= 6 \times 216 = 1296 = 36^2; \\
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= 144; & T_{16} &:= 4 \times 144 = 576 = 24^2; \\
 & & T_4 &:= 144 = 12^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

80	10	12	14	15	78	76	74	82
75	66	26	28	29	64	62	68	23
77	63	58	54	39	38	56	35	21
79	65	43	46	51	50	55	33	19
81	67	41	53	49	45	57	31	17
13	27	61	48	47	52	37	71	85
11	25	42	44	59	60	40	73	87
9	30	72	70	69	34	36	32	89
16	88	86	84	83	20	22	24	18

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{9 \times 9} &:= 441; & T_{81} &:= 9 \times 441 = 3969 = 63^2; \\
 S_{7 \times 7} &:= 343; & T_{49} &:= 7 \times 343 = 2401 = 49^2; \\
 S_{5 \times 5} &:= 245; & T_{25} &:= 5 \times 245 = 1225 = 35^2; \\
 S_{3 \times 3} &:= 147; & T_9 &:= 3 \times 123 = 441 = 21^2; \\
 & & T_1 &:= 49 = 7^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

There are five examples for **bordered** magic squares of order 8 and 9 resulting in **perfect square sum** of entries. Out of these five there are only three sums in each case. See below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= 512 = 8^3; & T_{64} &:= 8 \times 512 = 4096 = 64^2 = 8^4; \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= 800; & T_{64} &:= 8 \times 800 = 6400 = 80^2; \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= 288; & T_{64} &:= 8 \times 288 = 2304 = 48^2;
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{9 \times 9} &:= 729 = 9^3; & T_{81} &:= 9 \times 729 = 6561 = 81^2 = 9^4; \\
 S_{9 \times 9} &:= 1089 = 9^3; & T_{81} &:= 9 \times 1089 = 9801 = 99^2; \\
 S_{9 \times 9} &:= 441; & T_{81} &:= 9 \times 441 = 3969 = 63^2;
 \end{aligned}$$

The first case is due to **uniformity property**. The second case is due to **Pythagorean triples**. The last one is with **minimum perfect square sum** of entries. The aim of this work is write only the bordered magic squares of orders 3 to 47 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries. The subsection below give the list of magic square with their respective entries.

1.5 List of Magic Squares

According to formula given in equation (5), below is a list of magic square with entries as **natural numbers** for **odd order magic squares** and **fraction numbers** for **even order magic squares**. Each row brings in sequence as **magic order, magic sum, total sum of entries**. These entries results in **minimum perfect square sum**.

1. **Order 3**, $S_{3 \times 3} := 12$, $T_9 := 36 = 6^2$, $E := \{0, 1, \dots, 7, 8\}$
2. **Order 4**, $S_{4 \times 4} := 36$, $T_{16} := 144 = 12^2$, $E := \{3/2, 5/2, \dots, 31/2, 33/2\}$
3. **Order 5**, $S_{5 \times 5} := 80$, $T_{25} := 400 = 20^2$, $E := \{4, 5, \dots, 27, 28\}$
4. **Order 6**, $S_{6 \times 6} := 150$, $T_{36} := 900 = 30^2$, $E := \{15/2, 17/2, \dots, 83/2, 85/2\}$
5. **Order 7**, $S_{7 \times 7} := 175$, $T_{49} := 1225 = 35^2$, $E := \{1, 2, \dots, 48, 49\}$
6. **Order 8**, $S_{8 \times 8} := 288$, $T_{64} := 2304 = 48^2$, $E := \{9/2, 11/2, \dots, 133/2, 135/2\}$
7. **Order 9**, $S_{9 \times 9} := 441$, $T_{81} := 3969 = 63^2$, $E := \{9, 10, \dots, 88, 89\}$
8. **Order 10**, $S_{10 \times 10} := 640$, $T_{100} := 6400 = 80^2$, $E := \{29/2, 31/2, \dots, 225/2, 227/2\}$
9. **Order 11**, $S_{11 \times 11} := 704$, $T_{121} := 7744 = 88^2$, $E := \{4, 5, \dots, 123, 124\}$
10. **Order 12**, $S_{12 \times 12} := 972$, $T_{144} := 11664 = 108^2$, $E := \{19/2, 21/2, \dots, 303/2, 305/2\}$
11. **Order 13**, $S_{13 \times 13} := 1300$, $T_{169} := 16900 = 130^2$, $E := \{16, 17, \dots, 183, 184\}$
12. **Order 14**, $S_{14 \times 14} := 1400$, $T_{196} := 19600 = 140^2$, $E := \{5/2, 7/2, \dots, 393/2, 395/2\}$
13. **Order 15**, $S_{15 \times 15} := 1815$, $T_{225} := 27225 = 165^2$, $E := \{9, 10, \dots, 232, 233\}$
14. **Order 16**, $S_{16 \times 16} := 2304$, $T_{256} := 36864 = 192^2$, $E := \{33/2, 35/2, \dots, 541/2, 543/2\}$
15. **Order 17**, $S_{17 \times 17} := 2448$, $T_{289} := 41616 = 204^2$, $E := \{0, 1, \dots, 287, 288\}$
16. **Order 18**, $S_{18 \times 18} := 3042$, $T_{324} := 54756 = 234^2$, $E := \{15/2, 17/2, \dots, 659/2, 661/2\}$
17. **Order 19**, $S_{19 \times 19} := 3724$, $T_{361} := 70756 = 266^2$, $E := \{16, 17, \dots, 375, 376\}$
18. **Order 20**, $S_{20 \times 20} := 4500$, $T_{400} := 90000 = 300^2$, $E := \{51/2, 53/2, \dots, 847/2, 849/2\}$
19. **Order 21**, $S_{21 \times 21} := 4725$, $T_{441} := 99225 = 315^2$, $E := \{5, 6, \dots, 444, 445\}$
20. **Order 22**, $S_{22 \times 22} := 5632$, $T_{484} := 123904 = 352^2$, $E := \{29/2, 31/2, \dots, 993/2, 995/2\}$
21. **Order 23**, $S_{23 \times 23} := 6647$, $T_{529} := 152881 = 391^2$, $E := \{25, 26, \dots, 552, 553\}$
22. **Order 24**, $S_{24 \times 24} := 6936$, $T_{576} := 166464 = 408^2$, $E := \{3/2, 5/2, \dots, 1151/2, 1153/2\}$
23. **Order 25**, $S_{25 \times 25} := 8100$, $T_{625} := 202500 = 450^2$, $E := \{12, 13, \dots, 635, 636\}$

24. **Order 26**, $S_{26 \times 26} := 9386$, $T_{676} := 244036 = 494^2$, $E := \{47/2, 49/2, \dots, 1395/2, 1397/2\}$
25. **Order 27**, $S_{27 \times 27} := 10800$, $T_{729} := 291600 = 540^2$, $E := \{36, 37, \dots, 763, 764\}$
26. **Order 28**, $S_{28 \times 28} := 11200$, $T_{784} := 313600 = 560^2$, $E := \{17/2, 19/2, \dots, 1581/2, 1583/2\}$
27. **Order 29**, $S_{29 \times 29} := 12789$, $T_{841} := 370881 = 609^2$, $E := \{21, 22, \dots, 860, 861\}$
28. **Order 30**, $S_{30 \times 30} := 14520$, $T_{900} := 435600 = 660^2$, $E := \{69/2, 71/2, \dots, 1865/2, 1867/2\}$
29. **Order 31**, $S_{31 \times 31} := 15004$, $T_{961} := 465124 = 682^2$, $E := \{4, 5, \dots, 963, 964\}$
30. **Order 32**, $S_{32 \times 32} := 16928$, $T_{1024} := 541696 = 736^2$, $E := \{35/2, 37/2, \dots, 2079/2, 2081/2\}$
31. **Order 33**, $S_{33 \times 33} := 19008$, $T_{1089} := 627264 = 792^2$, $E := \{32, 33, \dots, 1119, 1120\}$
32. **Order 34**, $S_{34 \times 34} := 21250$, $T_{1156} := 722500 = 850^2$, $E := \{95/2, 97/2, \dots, 2403/2, 2405/2\}$
33. **Order 35**, $S_{35 \times 35} := 21875$, $T_{1225} := 765625 = 875^2$, $E := \{13, 14, \dots, 1236, 1237\}$
34. **Order 36**, $S_{36 \times 36} := 24336$, $T_{1296} := 876096 = 936^2$, $E := \{57/2, 59/2, \dots, 2645/2, 2647/2\}$
35. **Order 37**, $S_{37 \times 37} := 26973$, $T_{1369} := 998001 = 999^2$, $E := \{45, 46, \dots, 1412, 1413\}$
36. **Order 38**, $S_{38 \times 38} := 27702$, $T_{1444} := 1052676 = 1026^2$, $E := \{15/2, 17/2, \dots, 2899/2, 2901/2\}$
37. **Order 39**, $S_{39 \times 39} := 30576$, $T_{1521} := 1192464 = 1092^2$, $E := \{24, 25, \dots, 1543, 1544\}$
38. **Order 40**, $S_{40 \times 40} := 33640$, $T_{1600} := 1345600 = 1160^2$, $E := \{83/2, 85/2, \dots, 3279/2, 3281/2\}$
39. **Order 41**, $S_{41 \times 41} := 34481$, $T_{1681} := 1413721 = 1189^2$, $E := \{1, 2, \dots, 1680, 1681\}$
40. **Order 42**, $S_{42 \times 42} := 37800$, $T_{1764} := 1587600 = 1260^2$, $E := \{37/2, 39/2, \dots, 3561/2, 3563/2\}$
41. **Order 43**, $S_{43 \times 43} := 41323$, $T_{1849} := 1776889 = 1333^2$, $E := \{37, 38, \dots, 1884, 1885\}$
42. **Order 44**, $S_{44 \times 44} := 45056$, $T_{1936} := 1982464 = 1408^2$, $E := \{113/2, 115/2, \dots, 3981/2, 3983/2\}$
43. **Order 45**, $S_{45 \times 45} := 46080$, $T_{2025} := 2073600 = 1440^2$, $E := \{12, 13, \dots, 2035, 2036\}$
44. **Order 46**, $S_{46 \times 46} := 50094$, $T_{2116} := 2304324 = 1518^2$, $E := \{63/2, 65/2, \dots, 4291/2, 4293/2\}$
45. **Order 47**, $S_{47 \times 47} := 54332$, $T_{2209} := 2553604 = 1598^2$, $E := \{52, 53, \dots, 2259, 2260\}$

The letter E represents **consecutive natural or fraction numbers** entries; S represents magic square sum and T represents sum of entries resulting in **perfect squares**. The sum of entries results in magic squares always **minimum perfect squares**.

Remark 1.1(i) In case of **odd order** magic squares, the entries are **consecutive natural numbers**. In case of **even order** magic squares, the entries are **consecutive fraction numbers**.

(ii) Amongst the magic squares studied here the magic squares of orders 7 and 41 are the only ones starting with the number

1 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries. According to Sloane [2], the next magic square with **consecutive natural numbers** entries starting with the number 1 that yields a **minimum perfect square sum** of entries are of orders, 7, 41, 239, etc.

(iii) The magic square of orders 3 and 17 are the only two among the studied starts from 0 giving **minimum perfect square sum** of entries. It should be noted that we are only examining **positive entries** for the magic squares.

(iv) We can also obtain **perfect square sum** of entries for negative values, but these situations are not under study.

The sections below works on magic squares of orders 32 to 47 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries. The results for the magic squares orders 3 to 31 are given in author's another work [?]

2 Magic Squares of Order 32

This section brings **bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares of orders 32 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

The magic sums with their respective **perfect square sum** of entries are as follows:

$$S_{32 \times 32} := 16928; \quad T_{1024} := 32 \times 16928 = 541696 = 736^2;$$

$$S_{30 \times 30} := 15870; \quad T_{900} := 30 \times 15870 = 476100 = 690^2;$$

$$S_{28 \times 28} := 14812; \quad T_{784} := 28 \times 14812 = 414736 = 644^2;$$

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 13754; \quad T_{676} := 26 \times 13754 = 357604 = 598^2;$$

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 12696; \quad T_{576} := 24 \times 12696 = 304704 = 552^2;$$

$$S_{22 \times 22} := 11638; \quad T_{484} := 22 \times 11638 = 256036 = 506^2;$$

$$S_{20 \times 20} := 10580; \quad T_{400} := 20 \times 10580 = 211600 = 460^2;$$

$$S_{18 \times 18} := 9522; \quad T_{324} := 18 \times 9522 = 171396 = 414^2;$$

$$S_{16 \times 16} := 8464; \quad T_{256} := 16 \times 8464 = 135424 = 368^2;$$

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 7406; \quad T_{196} := 14 \times 7406 = 103684 = 322^2;$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 6348; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 6348 = 76176 = 276^2;$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 5290; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 5290 = 52900 = 230^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 4232; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 4232 = 33856 = 184^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 3174; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 3174 = 19044 = 138^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 2116; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 2116 = 8464 = 92^2;$$

$$T_4 := 2116 := 46^2.$$

It is formed by 16 blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 8 with equal magic sums. In this case, the magic sums with their respective **perfect square sum** of entries are as follows:

$$S_{32 \times 32} := 16928; \quad T_{1024} := 32 \times 16928 = 541696 = 736^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 4232; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 4232 = 33856 = 184^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 3174; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 3174 = 19044 = 138^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 2116; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 2116 = 8464 = 92^2;$$

$$T_4 := 2116 := 46^2.$$

3 Bordered Magic Square of Order 33

This section brings **bordered** magic square of order 33 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

The magic sums with their respective **perfect square sum** of entries are as follows:

$$\begin{array}{ll} \mathbf{S}_{33 \times 33} := 19008; & \mathbf{T}_{1089} := 33 \times 19008 = 627264 = 792^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{31 \times 31} := 17856; & \mathbf{T}_{961} := 31 \times 17856 = 553536 = 744^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{29 \times 29} := 16704; & \mathbf{T}_{841} := 29 \times 16704 = 484416 = 696^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{27 \times 27} := 15552; & \mathbf{T}_{729} := 27 \times 15552 = 419904 = 648^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{25 \times 25} := 14400; & \mathbf{T}_{625} := 25 \times 14400 = 360000 = 600^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{23 \times 23} := 13248; & \mathbf{T}_{529} := 23 \times 13248 = 304704 = 552^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{21 \times 21} := 12096; & \mathbf{T}_{441} := 21 \times 12096 = 254016 = 504^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{19 \times 19} := 10944; & \mathbf{T}_{361} := 19 \times 10944 = 207936 = 456^2; \\ & \mathbf{T}_1 := 576 = 24^2. \end{array}$$

4 Magic Squares of Order 34

This section brings **bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares of orders 34 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

The magic sums with their respective **perfect square sum** of entries are as follows:

$$S_{34 \times 34} := 21250; \quad T_{1156} := 34 \times 21250 = 722500 = 850^2;$$

$$S_{32 \times 32} := 20000; \quad T_{1024} := 32 \times 20000 = 640000 = 800^2;$$

$$S_{30 \times 30} := 18750; \quad T_{900} := 30 \times 18750 = 562500 = 750^2;$$

$$S_{28 \times 28} := 17500; \quad T_{784} := 28 \times 17500 = 490000 = 700^2;$$

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 16250; \quad T_{676} := 26 \times 16250 = 422500 = 650^2;$$

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 15000; \quad T_{576} := 24 \times 15000 = 360000 = 600^2;$$

$$S_{22 \times 22} := 13750; \quad T_{484} := 22 \times 13750 = 302500 = 550^2;$$

$$S_{20 \times 20} := 12500; \quad T_{400} := 20 \times 12500 = 250000 = 500^2;$$

$$S_{18 \times 18} := 11250; \quad T_{324} := 18 \times 11250 = 202500 = 450^2;$$

$$S_{16 \times 16} := 10000; \quad T_{256} := 16 \times 10000 = 160000 = 400^2;$$

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 8750; \quad T_{196} := 14 \times 8750 = 122500 = 350^2;$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 7500; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 7500 = 90000 = 300^2;$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 6250; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 6250 = 62500 = 250^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 5000; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 5000 = 40000 = 200^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 3750; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 3750 = 22500 = 150^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 2500; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 2500 = 10000 = 100^2;$$

$$T_4 := 2500 := 50^2.$$

It is formed by inner block of magic square of order 32 with 16 blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 8 with equal magic sums. The magic sums with their respective **perfect square sum** of entries are as follows:

$$S_{34 \times 34} := 21250; \quad T_{1156} := 34 \times 21250 = 722500 = 850^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 3750; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 3750 = 22500 = 150^2;$$

$$S_{32 \times 32} := 20000; \quad T_{1024} := 32 \times 20000 = 640000 = 800^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 2500; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 2500 = 10000 = 100^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 5000; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 5000 = 40000 = 200^2;$$

$$T_4 := 2500 = 50^2.$$

5 Bordered Magic Square of Order 35

This section brings **bordered** magic square of order 35 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

The magic sums with their respective **perfect square sum** of entries are as follows:

$$\begin{array}{ll} \mathbf{S}_{35 \times 35} := 21875; & \mathbf{T}_{1225} := 35 \times 21875 = 765625 = 875^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{33 \times 33} := 20625; & \mathbf{T}_{1089} := 33 \times 20625 = 680625 = 825^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{31 \times 31} := 19375; & \mathbf{T}_{961} := 31 \times 19375 = 600625 = 775^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{29 \times 29} := 18125; & \mathbf{T}_{841} := 29 \times 18125 = 525625 = 725^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{27 \times 27} := 16875; & \mathbf{T}_{729} := 27 \times 16875 = 455625 = 675^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{25 \times 25} := 15625; & \mathbf{T}_{625} := 25 \times 15625 = 390625 = 625^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{23 \times 23} := 14375; & \mathbf{T}_{529} := 23 \times 14375 = 330625 = 575^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{21 \times 21} := 13125; & \mathbf{T}_{441} := 21 \times 13125 = 275625 = 525^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{19 \times 19} := 11875; & \mathbf{T}_{361} := 19 \times 11875 = 225625 = 475^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{17 \times 17} := 10625; & \mathbf{T}_{289} := 17 \times 10625 = 180625 = 425^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{15 \times 15} := 9375; & \mathbf{T}_{225} := 15 \times 9375 = 140625 = 375^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{13 \times 13} := 8125; & \mathbf{T}_{169} := 13 \times 8125 = 105625 = 325^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{11 \times 11} := 6875; & \mathbf{T}_{121} := 11 \times 6875 = 75625 = 275^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{9 \times 9} := 5625; & \mathbf{T}_{81} := 9 \times 5625 = 50625 = 225^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{7 \times 7} := 4375; & \mathbf{T}_{49} := 7 \times 4375 = 30625 = 175^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{5 \times 5} := 3125; & \mathbf{T}_{25} := 5 \times 3125 = 15625 = 125^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{3 \times 3} := 1875; & \mathbf{T}_9 := 3 \times 1875 = 5625 = 75^2; \\ & \mathbf{T}_1 := 625 = 25^2. \end{array}$$

6 Magic Squares of Order 36

This section brings **bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares of orders 36 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

The magic sums with their respective **perfect square sum** of entries are as follows:

$$S_{36 \times 36} := 24336; \quad T_{1296} := 36 \times 24336 = 876096 = 936^2;$$

$$S_{34 \times 34} := 22984; \quad T_{1156} := 34 \times 22984 = 781456 = 884^2;$$

$$S_{32 \times 32} := 21632; \quad T_{1024} := 32 \times 21632 = 692224 = 832^2;$$

$$S_{30 \times 30} := 20280; \quad T_{900} := 30 \times 20280 = 608400 = 780^2;$$

$$S_{28 \times 28} := 18928; \quad T_{784} := 28 \times 18928 = 529984 = 728^2;$$

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 17576; \quad T_{676} := 26 \times 17576 = 456976 = 676^2;$$

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 16224; \quad T_{576} := 24 \times 16224 = 389376 = 624^2;$$

$$S_{22 \times 22} := 14872; \quad T_{484} := 22 \times 14872 = 327184 = 572^2;$$

$$S_{20 \times 20} := 13520; \quad T_{400} := 20 \times 13520 = 270400 = 520^2;$$

$$S_{18 \times 18} := 12168; \quad T_{324} := 18 \times 12168 = 219024 = 468^2;$$

$$S_{16 \times 16} := 10816; \quad T_{256} := 16 \times 10816 = 173056 = 416^2;$$

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 9464; \quad T_{196} := 14 \times 9464 = 132496 = 364^2;$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 8112; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 8112 = 97344 = 312^2;$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 6760; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 6760 = 67600 = 260^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 5408; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 5408 = 43264 = 208^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 4056; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 4056 = 24336 = 156^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 2704; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 2704 = 10816 = 104^2;$$

$$T_4 := 2704 := 52^2.$$

It is formed by 36 blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 6 with equal magic sums. In this case, the magic sums with their respective **perfect square sum** of entries are as follows:

$$S_{36 \times 36} := 24336; \quad T_{1296} := 36 \times 24336 = 876096 = 936^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 2704; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 2704 = 10816 = 104^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 4056; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 4056 = 24336 = 156^2;$$

$$T_4 := 2704 := 52^2.$$

7 Bordered Magic Square of Order 37

This section brings **bordered** magic square of order 37 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

The magic sums with their respective **perfect square sum** of entries are as follows:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \mathbf{S}_{37 \times 37} := 26973; & \mathbf{T}_{1369} := 37 \times 26973 = 998001 = 999^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{35 \times 35} := 25515; & \mathbf{T}_{1225} := 35 \times 25515 = 893025 = 945^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{33 \times 33} := 24057; & \mathbf{T}_{1089} := 33 \times 24057 = 793881 = 891^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{31 \times 31} := 22599; & \mathbf{T}_{961} := 31 \times 22599 = 700569 = 837^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{29 \times 29} := 21141; & \mathbf{T}_{841} := 29 \times 21141 = 613089 = 783^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{27 \times 27} := 19683; & \mathbf{T}_{729} := 27 \times 19683 = 531441 = 729^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{25 \times 25} := 18225; & \mathbf{T}_{625} := 25 \times 18225 = 455625 = 675^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{23 \times 23} := 16767; & \mathbf{T}_{529} := 23 \times 16767 = 385641 = 621^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{21 \times 21} := 15309; & \mathbf{T}_{441} := 21 \times 15309 = 321489 = 567^2; \\
 & \\
 \mathbf{S}_{19 \times 19} := 13851; & \mathbf{T}_{361} := 19 \times 13851 = 263169 = 513^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{17 \times 17} := 12393; & \mathbf{T}_{289} := 17 \times 12393 = 210681 = 459^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{15 \times 15} := 10935; & \mathbf{T}_{225} := 15 \times 10935 = 164025 = 405^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{13 \times 13} := 9477; & \mathbf{T}_{169} := 13 \times 9477 = 123201 = 351^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{11 \times 11} := 8019; & \mathbf{T}_{121} := 11 \times 8019 = 88209 = 297^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{9 \times 9} := 6561; & \mathbf{T}_{81} := 9 \times 6561 = 59049 = 243^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{7 \times 7} := 5103; & \mathbf{T}_{49} := 7 \times 5103 = 35721 = 189^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{5 \times 5} := 3645; & \mathbf{T}_{25} := 5 \times 3645 = 18225 = 135^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{3 \times 3} := 2187; & \mathbf{T}_9 := 3 \times 2187 = 6561 = 81^2; \\
 & \mathbf{T}_1 := 729 = 27^2.
 \end{array}$$

8 Magic Squares of Order 38

This section brings **bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares of orders 38 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

The magic sums with their respective **perfect square sum** of entries are as follows:

$$S_{38 \times 38} := 27702; \quad T_{1444} := 38 \times 27702 = 1052676 = 1026^2;$$

$$S_{36 \times 36} := 26244; \quad T_{1296} := 36 \times 26244 = 944784 = 972^2;$$

$$S_{34 \times 34} := 24786; \quad T_{1156} := 34 \times 24786 = 842724 = 918^2;$$

$$S_{32 \times 32} := 23328; \quad T_{1024} := 32 \times 23328 = 746496 = 864^2;$$

$$S_{30 \times 30} := 21870; \quad T_{900} := 30 \times 21870 = 656100 = 810^2;$$

$$S_{28 \times 28} := 20412; \quad T_{784} := 28 \times 20412 = 571536 = 756^2;$$

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 18954; \quad T_{676} := 26 \times 18954 = 492804 = 702^2;$$

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 17496; \quad T_{576} := 24 \times 17496 = 419904 = 648^2;$$

$$S_{22 \times 22} := 16038; \quad T_{484} := 22 \times 16038 = 352836 = 594^2;$$

$$S_{20 \times 20} := 14580; \quad T_{400} := 20 \times 14580 = 291600 = 540^2;$$

$$S_{18 \times 18} := 13122; \quad T_{324} := 18 \times 13122 = 236196 = 486^2;$$

$$S_{16 \times 16} := 11664; \quad T_{256} := 16 \times 11664 = 186624 = 432^2;$$

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 10206; \quad T_{196} := 14 \times 10206 = 142884 = 378^2;$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 8748; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 8748 = 104976 = 324^2;$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 7290; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 7290 = 72900 = 270^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 5832; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 5832 = 46656 = 216^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 4374; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 4374 = 26244 = 162^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 2916; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 2916 = 11664 = 108^2;$$

$$T_4 := 2916 := 54^2.$$

It is formed by inner block of magic square of order 36 with 9 blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 12 with equal magic sums. The magic sums with their respective sum of entries resulting in **perfect square sums** are as follows:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \mathbf{S}_{38 \times 38} := 27702; & \mathbf{T}_{1444} := 38 \times 27702 = 1052676 = 1026^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{36 \times 36} := 26244; & \mathbf{T}_{1296} := 36 \times 26244 = 944784 = 972^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{12 \times 12} := 8748; & \mathbf{T}_{144} := 12 \times 8748 = 104976 = 324^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{10 \times 10} := 7290; & \mathbf{T}_{100} := 10 \times 7290 = 72900 = 270^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{8 \times 8} := 5832; & \mathbf{T}_{64} := 8 \times 5832 = 46656 = 216^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{6 \times 6} := 4374; & \mathbf{T}_{36} := 6 \times 4374 = 26244 = 162^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{4 \times 4} := 2916; & \mathbf{T}_{16} := 4 \times 2916 = 11664 = 108^2; \\
 & \mathbf{T}_4 := 2916 := 54^2.
 \end{array}$$

Remark 8.1. The A **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 38 given in Example 11 is formed by inner block of magic square of order 36 with 9 blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 12 with equal magic sums. While in Example 8 we consider magic square of order 36 formed by equal sum blocks of order 6. This we have done two different way to show that, one can write **block-wise bordered** magic squares in different ways. In some cases, it is not necessary the the sub-blocks are of equal sums. For example, the same Example 8 can also be written as blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 9, but in this case these are with different magic sums. For more details see author's work [?].

9 Bordered Magic Square of Order 39

This section brings **bordered** magic square of order 39 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

The magic sums with their respective **perfect square sum** of entries are as follows:

$$\begin{array}{ll} S_{39 \times 39} := 30576; & T_{1521} := 39 \times 30576 = 1192464 = 1092^2; \\ S_{37 \times 37} := 29008; & T_{1369} := 37 \times 29008 = 1073296 = 1036^2; \\ S_{35 \times 35} := 27440; & T_{1225} := 35 \times 27440 = 960400 = 980^2; \\ S_{33 \times 33} := 25872; & T_{1089} := 33 \times 25872 = 853776 = 924^2; \\ S_{31 \times 31} := 24304; & T_{961} := 31 \times 24304 = 753424 = 868^2; \\ S_{29 \times 29} := 22736; & T_{841} := 29 \times 22736 = 659344 = 812^2; \\ S_{27 \times 27} := 21168; & T_{729} := 27 \times 21168 = 571536 = 756^2; \\ S_{25 \times 25} := 19600; & T_{625} := 25 \times 19600 = 490000 = 700^2; \\ S_{23 \times 23} := 18032; & T_{529} := 23 \times 18032 = 414736 = 644^2; \\ S_{21 \times 21} := 16464; & T_{441} := 21 \times 16464 = 345744 = 588^2; \\ S_{19 \times 19} := 14896; & T_{361} := 19 \times 14896 = 283024 = 532^2; \\ S_{17 \times 17} := 13328; & T_{289} := 17 \times 13328 = 226576 = 476^2; \\ S_{15 \times 15} := 11760; & T_{225} := 15 \times 11760 = 176400 = 420^2; \\ S_{13 \times 13} := 10192; & T_{169} := 13 \times 10192 = 132496 = 364^2; \\ S_{11 \times 11} := 8624; & T_{121} := 11 \times 8624 \times 94864 = 308^2; \\ S_{9 \times 9} := 7056; & T_{81} := 9 \times 7056 = 63504 = 252^2; \\ S_{7 \times 7} := 5488; & T_{49} := 7 \times 5488 = 38416 = 196^2; \\ S_{5 \times 5} := 3920; & T_{25} := 5 \times 3920 = 19600 = 140^2; \\ S_{3 \times 3} := 2352; & T_9 := 3 \times 2352 = 7056 = 84^2; \\ & T_1 := 784 = 28^2. \end{array}$$

10 Magic Squares of Order 40

This section brings **bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares of orders 40 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

The magic sums with their respective **perfect square sum** of entries are as follows:

$$S_{40 \times 40} := 33640; \quad T_{1600} := 40 \times 33640 = 1345600 = 1160^2;$$

$$S_{38 \times 38} := 31958; \quad T_{1444} := 38 \times 31958 = 1214404 = 1102^2;$$

$$S_{36 \times 36} := 30276; \quad T_{1296} := 36 \times 30276 = 1089936 = 1044^2;$$

$$S_{34 \times 34} := 28594; \quad T_{1156} := 34 \times 28594 = 972196 = 986^2;$$

$$S_{32 \times 32} := 26912; \quad T_{1024} := 32 \times 26912 = 861184 = 928^2;$$

$$S_{30 \times 30} := 25230; \quad T_{900} := 30 \times 25230 = 756900 = 870^2;$$

$$S_{28 \times 28} := 23548; \quad T_{784} := 28 \times 23548 = 659344 = 812^2;$$

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 21866; \quad T_{676} := 26 \times 21866 = 568516 = 754^2;$$

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 20184; \quad T_{576} := 24 \times 20184 = 484416 = 696^2;$$

$$S_{22 \times 22} := 18502; \quad T_{484} := 22 \times 18502 = 407044 = 638^2;$$

$$S_{20 \times 20} := 16820; \quad T_{400} := 20 \times 16820 = 336400 = 580^2;$$

$$S_{18 \times 18} := 15138; \quad T_{324} := 18 \times 15138 = 272484 = 522^2;$$

$$S_{16 \times 16} := 13456; \quad T_{256} := 16 \times 13456 = 215296 = 464^2;$$

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 11774; \quad T_{196} := 14 \times 11774 = 164836 = 406^2;$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 10092; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 10092 = 121104 = 348^2;$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 8410; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 8410 = 84100 := 290^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 6728; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 6728 = 53824 = 232^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 5046; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 5046 = 30276 = 174^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 3364; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 3364 = 13456 := 116^2;$$

$$T_4 := 3364 := 58^2.$$

It is formed by 16 blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 10 with equal magic sums. In this case, the magic sums with their respective **perfect square sum** of entries are as follows:

$$S_{40 \times 40} := 33640; \quad T_{1600} := 40 \times 33640 = 1345600 = 1160^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 5046; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 5046 = 30276 = 174^2;$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 8410; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 8410 = 84100 = 290^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 3364; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 3364 = 13456 = 116^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 6728; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 6728 = 53824 = 232^2;$$

$$T_4 := 3364 := 58^2.$$

11 Bordered Magic Square of Order 41

This section brings **bordered** magic square of order 41 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

The magic sums with their respective **perfect square sum** of entries are as follows:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 S_{41 \times 41} := 34481; & T_{1681} := 41 \times 34481 = 1413721 = 1189^2; \\
 S_{39 \times 39} := 32799; & T_{1521} := 39 \times 32799 = 1279161 = 1131^2; \\
 S_{37 \times 37} := 31117; & T_{1369} := 37 \times 31117 = 1151329 = 1073^2; \\
 S_{35 \times 35} := 29435; & T_{1225} := 35 \times 29435 = 1030225 = 1015^2; \\
 S_{33 \times 33} := 27753; & T_{1089} := 33 \times 27753 = 915849 = 957^2; \\
 S_{31 \times 31} := 26071; & T_{961} := 31 \times 26071 = 808201 = 899^2; \\
 S_{29 \times 29} := 24389; & T_{841} := 29 \times 24389 = 707281 = 841^2; \\
 S_{27 \times 27} := 22707; & T_{729} := 27 \times 22707 = 613089 = 783^2; \\
 S_{25 \times 25} := 21025; & T_{625} := 25 \times 21025 = 525625 = 725^2; \\
 S_{23 \times 23} := 19343; & T_{529} := 23 \times 19343 = 444889 = 667^2; \\
 \\
 S_{21 \times 21} := 17661; & T_{441} := 21 \times 17661 = 370881 = 609^2; \\
 S_{19 \times 19} := 15979; & T_{361} := 19 \times 15979 = 303601 = 551^2; \\
 S_{17 \times 17} := 14297; & T_{289} := 17 \times 14297 = 243049 = 493^2; \\
 S_{15 \times 15} := 12615; & T_{225} := 15 \times 12615 = 189225 = 435^2; \\
 S_{13 \times 13} := 10933; & T_{169} := 13 \times 10933 = 142129 = 377^2; \\
 S_{11 \times 11} := 9251; & T_{121} := 11 \times 9251 = 101761 = 319^2; \\
 S_{9 \times 9} := 7569; & T_{81} := 9 \times 7569 = 68121 = 261^2; \\
 S_{7 \times 7} := 5887; & T_{49} := 7 \times 5887 = 41209 = 203^2; \\
 S_{5 \times 5} := 4205; & T_{25} := 5 \times 4205 = 21025 = 145^2; \\
 S_{3 \times 3} := 2523; & T_9 := 3 \times 2523 = 7569 = 87^2; \\
 & T_1 := 841 = 29^2.
 \end{array}$$

12 Magic Squares of Order 42

This section brings **bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares of orders 42 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

The magic sums with their respective **perfect square sum** of entries are as follows:

$$S_{42 \times 42} := 37800; \quad T_{1764} := 42 \times 37800 = 1587600 := 1260^2;$$

$$S_{40 \times 40} := 36000; \quad T_{1600} := 40 \times 36000 = 1440000 := 1200^2;$$

$$S_{38 \times 38} := 34200; \quad T_{1444} := 38 \times 34200 = 1299600 := 1140^2;$$

$$S_{36 \times 36} := 32400; \quad T_{1296} := 36 \times 32400 = 1166400 := 1080^2;$$

$$S_{34 \times 34} := 30600; \quad T_{1156} := 34 \times 30600 = 1040400 := 1020^2;$$

$$S_{32 \times 32} := 28800; \quad T_{1024} := 32 \times 28800 = 921600 := 960^2;$$

$$S_{30 \times 30} := 27000; \quad T_{900} := 30 \times 27000 = 810000 := 900^2;$$

$$S_{28 \times 28} := 25200; \quad T_{784} := 28 \times 25200 = 705600 := 840^2;$$

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 23400; \quad T_{676} := 26 \times 23400 = 608400 := 780^2;$$

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 21600; \quad T_{576} := 24 \times 21600 = 518400 := 720^2;$$

$$S_{22 \times 22} := 19800; \quad T_{484} := 22 \times 19800 = 435600 := 660^2;$$

$$S_{20 \times 20} := 18000; \quad T_{400} := 20 \times 18000 = 360000 := 600^2;$$

$$S_{18 \times 18} := 16200; \quad T_{324} := 18 \times 16200 = 291600 := 540^2;$$

$$S_{16 \times 16} := 14400; \quad T_{256} := 16 \times 14400 = 230400 := 480^2;$$

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 12600; \quad T_{196} := 14 \times 12600 = 176400 := 420^2;$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 10800; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 10800 = 129600 := 360^2;$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 9000; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 9000 = 90000 := 300^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 7200; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 7200 = 57600 := 240^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 5400; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 5400 = 32400 := 180^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 3600; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 3600 = 14400 := 120^2;$$

$$T_4 := 3600 := 60^2.$$

It is formed by 9 blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 14 with equal magic sums. In this case, the magic sums with their respective **perfect square sum** of entries are as follows:

$$S_{42 \times 42} := 37800; \quad T_{1764} := 42 \times 37800 = 1587600 := 1260^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 7200; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 7200 = 57600 := 240^2;$$

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 12600; \quad T_{196} := 14 \times 12600 = 176400 := 420^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 5400; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 5400 = 32400 := 180^2;$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 10800; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 10800 = 129600 := 360^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 3600; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 3600 = 14400 := 120^2;$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 9000; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 9000 = 90000 := 300^2;$$

$$T_4 := 3600 := 60^2.$$

13 Bordered Magic Square of Order 43

This section brings **bordered** magic square of order 43 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

The magic sums with their respective **perfect square sum** of entries are as follows:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \mathbf{S}_{43 \times 43} := 41323; & \mathbf{T}_{1849} := 43 \times 41323 = 1776889 = 1333^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{41 \times 41} := 39401; & \mathbf{T}_{1681} := 41 \times 39401 = 1615441 = 1271^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{39 \times 39} := 37479; & \mathbf{T}_{1521} := 39 \times 37479 = 1461681 = 1209^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{37 \times 37} := 35557; & \mathbf{T}_{1369} := 37 \times 35557 = 1315609 = 1147^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{35 \times 35} := 33635; & \mathbf{T}_{1225} := 35 \times 33635 = 1177225 = 1085^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{33 \times 33} := 31713; & \mathbf{T}_{1089} := 33 \times 31713 = 1046529 = 1023^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{31 \times 31} := 29791; & \mathbf{T}_{961} := 31 \times 29791 = 923521 = 961^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{29 \times 29} := 27869; & \mathbf{T}_{841} := 29 \times 27869 = 808201 = 899^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{27 \times 27} := 25947; & \mathbf{T}_{729} := 27 \times 25947 = 700569 = 837^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{25 \times 25} := 24025; & \mathbf{T}_{625} := 25 \times 24025 = 600625 = 775^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{23 \times 23} := 22103; & \mathbf{T}_{529} := 23 \times 22103 = 508369 = 713^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{21 \times 21} := 20181; & \mathbf{T}_{441} := 21 \times 20181 = 423801 = 651^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{19 \times 19} := 18259; & \mathbf{T}_{361} := 19 \times 18259 = 346921 = 589^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{17 \times 17} := 16337; & \mathbf{T}_{289} := 17 \times 16337 = 277729 = 527^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{15 \times 15} := 14415; & \mathbf{T}_{225} := 15 \times 14415 = 216225 = 465^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{13 \times 13} := 12493; & \mathbf{T}_{169} := 13 \times 12493 = 162409 = 403^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{11 \times 11} := 10571; & \mathbf{T}_{121} := 11 \times 10571 = 116281 = 341^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{9 \times 9} := 8649; & \mathbf{T}_{81} := 9 \times 8649 = 77841 = 279^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{7 \times 7} := 6727; & \mathbf{T}_{49} := 7 \times 6727 = 47089 = 217^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{5 \times 5} := 4805; & \mathbf{T}_{25} := 5 \times 4805 = 24025 = 155^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{3 \times 3} := 2883; & \mathbf{T}_9 := 3 \times 2883 = 8649 = 93^2; \\
 & \mathbf{T}_1 := 961 = 31^2.
 \end{array}$$

14 Magic Squares of Order 44

This section brings **bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares of orders 44 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

The magic sums with their respective **perfect square sum** of entries are as follows:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \mathbf{S}_{44 \times 44} := 45056; & \mathbf{T}_{1936} := 44 \times 45056 = 1982464 = 1408^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{42 \times 42} := 43008; & \mathbf{T}_{1764} := 42 \times 43008 = 1806336 = 1344^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{40 \times 40} := 40960; & \mathbf{T}_{1600} := 40 \times 40960 = 1638400 = 1280^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{38 \times 38} := 38912; & \mathbf{T}_{1444} := 38 \times 38912 = 1478656 = 1216^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{36 \times 36} := 36864; & \mathbf{T}_{1296} := 36 \times 36864 = 1327104 = 1152^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{34 \times 34} := 34816; & \mathbf{T}_{1156} := 34 \times 34816 = 1183744 = 1088^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{32 \times 32} := 32768; & \mathbf{T}_{1024} := 32 \times 32768 = 1048576 = 1024^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{30 \times 30} := 30720; & \mathbf{T}_{900} := 30 \times 30720 = 921600 = 960^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{28 \times 28} := 28672; & \mathbf{T}_{784} := 28 \times 28672 = 802816 = 896^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{26 \times 26} := 26624; & \mathbf{T}_{676} := 26 \times 26624 = 692224 = 832^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{24 \times 24} := 24576; & \mathbf{T}_{576} := 24 \times 24576 = 589824 = 768^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{22 \times 22} := 22528; & \mathbf{T}_{484} := 22 \times 22528 = 495616 = 704^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{20 \times 20} := 20480; & \mathbf{T}_{400} := 20 \times 20480 = 409600 = 640^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{18 \times 18} := 18432; & \mathbf{T}_{324} := 18 \times 18432 = 331776 = 576^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{16 \times 16} := 16384; & \mathbf{T}_{256} := 16 \times 16384 = 262144 = 512^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{14 \times 14} := 14336; & \mathbf{T}_{196} := 14 \times 14336 = 200704 = 448^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{12 \times 12} := 12288; & \mathbf{T}_{144} := 12 \times 12288 = 147456 = 384^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{10 \times 10} := 10240; & \mathbf{T}_{100} := 10 \times 10240 = 102400 = 320^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{8 \times 8} := 8192; & \mathbf{T}_{64} := 8 \times 8192 = 65536 = 256^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{6 \times 6} := 6144; & \mathbf{T}_{36} := 6 \times 6144 = 36864 = 192^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{4 \times 4} := 4096; & \mathbf{T}_{16} := 4 \times 4096 = 16384 = 128^2; \\
 & \mathbf{T}_4 := 4096 := 64^2.
 \end{array}$$

It is formed by inner block of magic square of order 42 with 9 blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 14 with equal magic sums. The magic sums with their respective sum of entries resulting in **perfect square sums** are as follows:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 S_{44 \times 44} := 45056; & T_{1936} := 44 \times 45056 = 1982464 = 1408^2; \\
 S_{42 \times 42} := 43008; & T_{1764} := 42 \times 43008 = 1806336 = 1344^2; \\
 S_{14 \times 14} := 14336; & T_{196} := 14 \times 14336 = 200704 = 448^2; \\
 S_{12 \times 12} := 12288; & T_{144} := 12 \times 12288 = 147456 = 384^2; \\
 S_{10 \times 10} := 10240; & T_{100} := 10 \times 10240 = 102400 = 320^2; \\
 S_{8 \times 8} := 8192; & T_{64} := 8 \times 8192 = 65536 = 256^2; \\
 S_{6 \times 6} := 6144; & T_{36} := 6 \times 6144 = 36864 = 192^2; \\
 S_{4 \times 4} := 4096; & T_{16} := 4 \times 4096 = 16384 = 128^2; \\
 & T_4 := 4096 = 64^2.
 \end{array}$$

Remark 14.1. *The A **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 44 given in Example 20 is formed by inner block of magic square of order 42 with 9 blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 14 with equal magic sums. It can also be written as blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 11 or 4. In case of order 11, the magic sums of order 11 are different. In case of order 4, the magic sums are equal, but to have different option, we opted the way written above.*

15 Bordered Magic Square of Order 45

This section brings **bordered** magic square of order 45 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

The magic sums with their respective **perfect square sum** of entries are as follows:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \mathbf{S}_{45 \times 45} := 46080; & \mathbf{T}_{2025} := 45 \times 46080 = 2073600 = 1440^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{43 \times 43} := 44032; & \mathbf{T}_{1849} := 43 \times 44032 = 1893376 = 1376^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{41 \times 41} := 41984; & \mathbf{T}_{1681} := 41 \times 41984 = 1721344 = 1312^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{39 \times 39} := 39936; & \mathbf{T}_{1521} := 39 \times 39936 = 1557504 = 1248^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{37 \times 37} := 37888; & \mathbf{T}_{1369} := 37 \times 37888 = 1401856 = 1184^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{35 \times 35} := 35840; & \mathbf{T}_{1225} := 35 \times 35840 = 1254400 = 1120^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{33 \times 33} := 33792; & \mathbf{T}_{1089} := 33 \times 33792 = 1115136 = 1056^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{31 \times 31} := 31744; & \mathbf{T}_{961} := 31 \times 31744 = 984064 = 992^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{29 \times 29} := 29696; & \mathbf{T}_{841} := 29 \times 29696 = 861184 = 928^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{27 \times 27} := 27648; & \mathbf{T}_{729} := 27 \times 27648 = 746496 = 864^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{25 \times 25} := 25600; & \mathbf{T}_{625} := 25 \times 25600 = 640000 = 800^2; \\
 \\
 \mathbf{S}_{23 \times 23} := 23552; & \mathbf{T}_{529} := 23 \times 23552 = 541696 = 736^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{21 \times 21} := 21504; & \mathbf{T}_{441} := 21 \times 21504 = 451584 = 672^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{19 \times 19} := 19456; & \mathbf{T}_{361} := 19 \times 19456 = 369664 = 608^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{17 \times 17} := 17408; & \mathbf{T}_{289} := 17 \times 17408 = 295936 = 544^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{15 \times 15} := 15360; & \mathbf{T}_{225} := 15 \times 15360 = 230400 = 480^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{13 \times 13} := 13312; & \mathbf{T}_{169} := 13 \times 13312 = 173056 = 416^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{11 \times 11} := 11264; & \mathbf{T}_{121} := 11 \times 11264 = 123904 = 352^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{9 \times 9} := 9216; & \mathbf{T}_{81} := 9 \times 9216 = 82944 = 288^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{7 \times 7} := 7168; & \mathbf{T}_{49} := 7 \times 7168 = 50176 = 224^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{5 \times 5} := 5120; & \mathbf{T}_{25} := 5 \times 5120 = 25600 = 160^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{3 \times 3} := 3072; & \mathbf{T}_9 := 3 \times 3072 = 9216 = 96^2; \\
 & \mathbf{T}_1 := 1024 = 32^2.
 \end{array}$$

16 Magic Squares of Order 46

This section brings **bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares of orders 46 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

The magic sums with their respective **perfect square sum** of entries are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{46 \times 46} &:= 50094; & T_{2116} &:= 46 \times 50094 = 2304324 = 1518^2; \\
 S_{44 \times 44} &:= 47916; & T_{1936} &:= 44 \times 47916 = 2108304 = 1452^2; \\
 S_{42 \times 42} &:= 45738; & T_{1764} &:= 42 \times 45738 = 1920996 = 1386^2; \\
 S_{40 \times 40} &:= 43560; & T_{1600} &:= 40 \times 43560 = 1742400 = 1320^2; \\
 S_{38 \times 38} &:= 41382; & T_{1444} &:= 38 \times 41382 = 1572516 = 1254^2; \\
 S_{36 \times 36} &:= 39204; & T_{1296} &:= 36 \times 39204 = 1411344 = 1188^2; \\
 S_{34 \times 34} &:= 37026; & T_{1156} &:= 34 \times 37026 = 1258884 = 1122^2; \\
 S_{32 \times 32} &:= 34848; & T_{1024} &:= 32 \times 34848 = 1115136 = 1056^2; \\
 S_{30 \times 30} &:= 32670; & T_{900} &:= 30 \times 32670 = 980100 = 990^2; \\
 S_{28 \times 28} &:= 30492; & T_{784} &:= 28 \times 30492 = 853776 = 924^2; \\
 S_{26 \times 26} &:= 28314; & T_{676} &:= 26 \times 28314 = 736164 = 858^2; \\
 S_{24 \times 24} &:= 26136; & T_{576} &:= 24 \times 26136 = 627264 = 792^2;
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{22 \times 22} &:= 23958; & T_{484} &:= 22 \times 23958 = 527076 = 726^2; \\
 S_{20 \times 20} &:= 21780; & T_{400} &:= 20 \times 21780 = 435600 = 660^2; \\
 S_{18 \times 18} &:= 19602; & T_{324} &:= 18 \times 19602 = 352836 = 594^2; \\
 S_{16 \times 16} &:= 17424; & T_{256} &:= 16 \times 17424 = 278784 = 528^2; \\
 S_{14 \times 14} &:= 15246; & T_{196} &:= 14 \times 15246 = 213444 = 462^2; \\
 S_{12 \times 12} &:= 13068; & T_{144} &:= 12 \times 13068 = 156816 = 396^2; \\
 S_{10 \times 10} &:= 10890; & T_{100} &:= 10 \times 10890 = 108900 = 330^2; \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= 8712; & T_{64} &:= 8 \times 8712 = 69696 = 264^2; \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= 6534; & T_{36} &:= 6 \times 6534 = 39204 = 198^2; \\
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= 4356; & T_{16} &:= 4 \times 4356 = 17424 = 132^2; \\
 & & T_4 &:= 4356 := 66^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

It is formed by two inner blocks of magic square of order 44 and 42. The inner block of order 42 is again formed by 49 blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 6 with equal magic sums. The magic sums with their respective sum of entries resulting in **perfect square sums** are as follows:

$$S_{46 \times 46} := 50094; \quad T_{2116} := 46 \times 50094 = 2304324 = 1518^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 6534; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 6534 = 39204 = 198^2;$$

$$S_{44 \times 44} := 47916; \quad T_{1936} := 44 \times 47916 = 2108304 = 1452^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 4356; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 4356 = 17424 = 132^2;$$

$$S_{42 \times 42} := 45738; \quad T_{1764} := 42 \times 45738 = 1920996 = 1386^2;$$

$$T_4 := 4356 := 66^2.$$

17 Bordered Magic Square of Order 47

This section brings **bordered** magic square of order 47 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

The magic sums with their respective **perfect square sum** of entries are as follows:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 S_{47 \times 47} := 54332; & T_{2209} := 47 \times 54332 = 2553604 = 1598^2; \\
 S_{45 \times 45} := 52020; & T_{2025} := 45 \times 52020 = 2340900 = 1530^2; \\
 S_{43 \times 43} := 49708; & T_{1849} := 43 \times 49708 = 2137444 = 1462^2; \\
 S_{41 \times 41} := 47396; & T_{1681} := 41 \times 47396 = 1943236 = 1394^2; \\
 S_{39 \times 39} := 45084; & T_{1521} := 39 \times 45084 = 1758276 = 1326^2; \\
 S_{37 \times 37} := 42772; & T_{1369} := 37 \times 42772 = 1582564 = 1258^2; \\
 S_{35 \times 35} := 40460; & T_{1225} := 35 \times 40460 = 1416100 = 1190^2; \\
 S_{33 \times 33} := 38148; & T_{1089} := 33 \times 38148 = 1258884 = 1122^2; \\
 S_{31 \times 31} := 35836; & T_{961} := 31 \times 35836 = 1110916 = 1054^2; \\
 S_{29 \times 29} := 33524; & T_{841} := 29 \times 33524 = 972196 = 986^2; \\
 S_{27 \times 27} := 31212; & T_{729} := 27 \times 31212 = 842724 = 918^2; \\
 S_{25 \times 25} := 28900; & T_{625} := 25 \times 28900 = 722500 = 850^2; \\
 S_{23 \times 23} := 26588; & T_{529} := 23 \times 26588 = 611524 = 782^2; \\
 S_{21 \times 21} := 24276; & T_{441} := 21 \times 24276 = 509796 = 714^2; \\
 S_{19 \times 19} := 21964; & T_{361} := 19 \times 21964 = 417316 = 646^2; \\
 S_{17 \times 17} := 19652; & T_{289} := 17 \times 19652 = 334084 = 578^2; \\
 S_{15 \times 15} := 17340; & T_{225} := 15 \times 17340 = 260100 = 510^2; \\
 S_{13 \times 13} := 15028; & T_{169} := 13 \times 15028 = 195364 = 442^2; \\
 S_{11 \times 11} := 12716; & T_{121} := 11 \times 12716 = 139876 = 374^2; \\
 S_{9 \times 9} := 10404; & T_{81} := 9 \times 10404 = 93636 = 306^2; \\
 S_{7 \times 7} := 8092; & T_{49} := 7 \times 8092 = 56644 = 238^2; \\
 S_{5 \times 5} := 5780; & T_{25} := 5 \times 5780 = 28900 = 170^2; \\
 S_{3 \times 3} := 3468; & T_9 := 3 \times 3468 = 10404 = 102^2; \\
 & T_1 := 1156 = 34^2.
 \end{array}$$

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Most of the **bordered** magic squares are calculated based on the software developed by Harry White [3, 4, ?]. Author is thankful to Harry White for keeping these software available at the link: <http://budshaw.ca/Download.html>.

18 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation of Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation of numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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textit<https://oeis.org/A001653>, Numbers k such that $2 \times k^2 - 1$ is a square

[3] **H. White**, Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/Download.html>

[4] **H. White**, Block Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/BlockSquares.html>

[5] **H. White**, Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/SODLS.html>

• Block-Wise Magic Squares

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